

Impact Study

Paleobiology

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Context

In the last 50 years, paleobiology has undergone a [computational revolution](#), opening new avenues for recording and analysing the history of life on Earth. Paleobiology is a branch of paleontology focused on the biology of fossil organisms, studying their origin, evolution and ecological context mostly through fossils and ancient biological materials over geological time scales.

This case study explores how the use of biodata resources focusing on paleobiology is leading to impacts across industry, technology and education, leveraging information from the ancient past to respond to the challenges we face today.

Industrial biostratigraphy

Firms such as [PetroStrat](#) and its subsidiary [Paleo Data](#) sell biostratigraphy services and fossil data products used for real-time wellsite decisions, geo-steering, casing points, de-risking subsurface models and improving operational efficiency. The value add of these services, which have contributed to “[some of the biggest oil and gas discoveries in the world](#),” is to reduce uncertainty and costs in exploration and development in the oil and gas sector.

The [Nannotax online taxonomy](#) is an open, standardised calcareous nannofossil reference, which is widely used by industry biostratigraphers because it is “[money- and time-saving](#).” Nannotax provides a single authoritative taxonomy that avoids costly inconsistencies when identifying fossils, as [multiple industry sources attest](#). For example, Mike Styzen, Senior Biostratigraphic Advisor at Noble Energy Inc, highlighted:

“Nannotax is the first place I look when I’m presented with a nannoplankton taxon that I am unfamiliar with. I am always working on multiple projects, and I don’t have time to dig through old books and new literature, so Nannotax is a real time saver. [...] The benefit is more reliable modeling of what we are drilling. In West Africa in particular I have data that ranges from 35 years old to freshly generated data. Nannotax is a key tool, allowing me to put together a picture of the basin histories, which means we can more efficiently develop the resources available in the area.”

The time-saving benefits of Nannotax readily translate into monetary savings for companies such as Shell, because the database can provide answers in seconds rather than hours or days. This means that the efficiency of biostratigraphic work is optimised and the interpretations can inform operational decisions in a more timely and cost-effective way.

Rui Da Gama, a biostratigrapher for Shell, added:

“One of Nannotax’s other key strengths is its ability to reconcile historic taxonomic terms to their modern equivalents. This is really important when reviewing data from sites that were deemed not economically viable when originally drilled in, for example, the 1970s, but which may well be viable now given recent advances in extraction technology. There is no doubt whatever that interaction between the environmental research and oil and gas communities can be highly beneficial to both parties, and that governments should encourage and support both relevant research and closer interaction between them.”

Additionally, in 2025, PetroStrat also hosted the [19th International Nannoplankton Association conference](#), which included discussions on how to improve Nannotax and welcomed 138 participants from 28 countries, including 28 industry representatives. The impact of Nannotax on industry is further highlighted by the decision of Woodside Energy and Shell US to [support the resource](#) over the course of 2024.

Learning in the air

[Flyover Country](#) built a mobile geoscience app to [ingest fossil data](#) from the [Paleobiology Database](#) and the [Neotoma Paleoecology Database](#), as well as geology data from [Macrostrat](#), to show passengers what fossils and formations they are overflying—offline, in airplane mode.

The [NSF-funded effort](#) demonstrates how accessible biodata resources enable new educational applications. Shane Loeffler, who worked on the FlyOverCountry mobile app integration, explains:

“Well documented and publicly accessible APIs for accessing data about the paleobiology of any region on Earth was key to being able to create educational experiences for users no matter where they found themselves. In our case the airplane window seemed like the perfect place to engage people about the richness of Earth’s history. Having easily accessible data for anywhere on Earth made the whole concept possible. Tools like the Paleobiology and Neotoma databases have been invaluable in making the Flyover Country app possible.”

The app's update history also reveals that, since creation, additional databases such as [Extending Ocean Drilling Pursuits \(eODP\)](#) and [NASA GLOBE Observer Alerts](#) have been integrated.

While Flyover Country was initially conceived as a tool to learn about the landscape below from an airplane window seat, it now includes a ground-based driving/walking mode as well. The app will provide location-based information, maps, photos and figures for field sites, making it useful for educational experiences in various settings. [Research](#) demonstrates that the Flyover Country app significantly enhances the accessibility, flexibility, and enjoyment of field-based learning in geoscience education, particularly at the introductory level, enabling comparable learning outcomes to traditional field trips while addressing barriers that often exclude students from these formative experiences.

Conclusions

These case studies show how paleobiology databases, by integrating biological and geological insights, extend far beyond purely academic pursuits and can deliver tangible benefits across industry, research and society.

As computational tools and open data initiatives continue to evolve, the potential for paleobiology to inform [sustainable practices](#), [technological development](#) and [scientific literacy](#) will only grow, reaffirming its role as a vital discipline at the intersection of history, science and society.

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Appendix – Resources discussed

Resources	About
Extending Ocean Drilling Pursuits	<p>The eODP (Extending Ocean Drilling Pursuits) is a database project that integrates paleoceanographic and paleobiological data from ocean drilling programs into unified, accessible repositories.</p> <p>The eODP consolidates data from the International Ocean Discovery Program and predecessor programs, which have collected sediment cores from ocean floors for over 50 years. These cores contain fossil and rock records extending back to the Jurassic period.</p>
GLOBE Observer	<p>The GLOBE Observer is a citizen science app allowing volunteers to take observations and contribute to the Global Learning and Observations to Benefit the Environment (GLOBE) community. The open database supports Earth system science research. It includes data on clouds, dust, mosquito habitats, and land coverage.</p>
Macrostrat	<p>Macrostrat is a platform for the aggregation and distribution of geological data relevant to the spatial and temporal distribution of sedimentary, igneous, and metamorphic rocks as well as data extracted from them. It is linked to the xDD (formerly GeoDeepDive) digital library and machine reading system, and it aims to become a community resource for the addition, editing, and distribution of new stratigraphic, lithological, environmental, and economic data. Interactive applications built upon Macrostrat are designed for educational and research purposes.</p>

Resources	About
<u>Nannotax online taxonomy</u>	<p>Nannotax is an online resource documenting nannofossil taxonomy. The aim of the Nannotax site is to provide an authoritative guide to the taxonomy and biodiversity of coccolithophores, a group of planktonic algae that play a key role in the global carbon cycle and have an extensive fossil record. The Nannotax project began in 2007 and the resource is widely used by nannofossil workers.</p>
<u>Neotoma Paleocology Database</u>	<p>The Neotoma Paleocology Database contains community-curated data relating to paleoecological and paleoenvironmental data. The primary focus of Neotoma is the geological record relating to the Pliocene-Quaternary period, during which humans evolved and developed modern ecosystems. Alongside data, Neotoma also provides underlying cyberinfrastructure to support development of software tools.</p>
<u>The Paleobiology Database</u>	<p>The Paleobiology Database, first established in 1998, is a paleontological database containing data related to fossil records, maintained by a group of international non-governmental paleontologists. The resource supports filtering of fossil occurrences through space, time, taxonomy, as well as modern and paleogeographic locations. Spanning organisms of all geological ages, the site also provides data services to support development of analytical tools and visualisation software.</p>

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